

ALS VOLUNTEERED TEACHERS TEACHING SPECIALIZED SUBJECTS: ITS EFFECT IN THE FUNCTIONAL LITERACY ACQUISITION

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the effect of ALS volunteered teachers teaching specialized subjects in the functional literacy acquisition of ALS students. This study solved the research problems qualitatively and quantitatively through the action research method. It can be delineated from the result of the study that most of the respondents strongly agreed that the effect of ALS volunteered teachers are veritably beneficial in enhancing their academic performance in ALS specifically in functional literacy in terms of communication skills, scientific and critical thinking skills, mathematical and problem-solving skills, understanding the self and society, life and career skills and digital citizenship. This study was delimited to the ALS students for the academic year 2022-2023. This study revealed the pedagogical strategies and interventions identified as best practices and processes in improving and developing the functional literacy of ALS students of ALS volunteered teachers. The research was crafted in line with the improvement of functional literacy in terms of communication skills, scientific and critical thinking skills, mathematical and problem-solving skills, understanding the self and society, life and career skills and digital citizenship.

Keywords: *Functional literacy, Alternative Learning System (ALS), Volunteered teachers*

INTRODUCTION

Several of the most important things to promote among ALS students is functional literacy. According to UNESCO (2006) as cited by Ocampo (2022) functional literacy is the ability to make substantial use of activities that include reading and writing skills, such as using information, communicating with others, and enrolling in a lifelong learning course, all of which are necessary for an individual's ability to express himself or herself in daily life. It can be used to assist a person in contributing to his or her own advancement as well as the advancement of his or her family and community. It includes both formal and informal engagement skills, as well as those requisite for national change and growth. (Miriam College, n.d.; PNA, 2020).

According to Ocampo (2021), citing Olupotunde (2014), a person who is illiterate is denied real opportunities to engage with democratic institutions to make educated choices, exercise rights as citizens, and act in the public interest. Illiteracy dwarfs a person's mind because they're unable to process information, which makes it hard to manage. This subset of skills is considered essential for success in today's society, especially in co – curricular courses and emerging career paths and places of employment and can be implemented in all scholarly areas of study as well as all academic, career, and civic configurations throughout a student's life (Moyer, 2016).

In line with this, the researcher believed that the quality of ALS teachers should not be delimited to one mentor as functional literacy comprises significant skills such as (a) communication skills, (b) scientific and critical thinking skills, (c) mathematical and problem-solving skills, (d) life and career skills, (e) understanding the self and society, and (f) digital citizenship (formerly digital literacy) (BSU, 2018); CEd, 2017).

To strengthen this, Dalig National High School best practices in educating ALS students' functional literacy is to provide volunteer teachers from Junior High School department to teach specialized subjects to align the needed competencies of ALS students.

In connection to this, the researchers determined the effect of ALS volunteered teachers teaching specialized subjects in the functional literacy acquisition of ALS students.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effect of ALS volunteered teachers in the functional literacy of ALS students. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What are the best practices of ALS volunteered teachers in developing the functional literacy of students?

2. What is the effect of ALS volunteered teachers in the functional literacy of ALS students in terms of:
 - 2.1 Communication skills (English and Filipino);
 - 2.2 Scientific and critical thinking skills;
 - 2.3 Mathematical and problem-solving skills;
 - 2.4 Understanding the self and society;
 - 2.5 Life and career skills; and
 - 2.6 Digital citizenship?
 3. What action plan can be proposed in developing the academic performance of students?
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METHODOLOGY

This study utilized descriptive-qualitative design since the researchers determined the effect of ALS volunteered teachers in the functional literacy of ALS students during the S.Y. 2022- 2023. Also, the study used qualitative study through observation and interview with the students and teachers as basis for action plan improvement. This study was delimited to ALS students as revealed in the result of the data gathered. Purposive sampling was utilized in determining the respondents of the study.

Data were collected through Gather ideas from interview and transcriptions of verbatim quotes, conversation with experts/third parties, and researcher-made questionnaire to determine the effect of ALS volunteered teachers in the functional literacy of ALS students. Statistically, frequency and weighted mean average were utilized to determine the effect of ALS volunteered teachers teaching specialized subjects to the functional literacy acquisition of ALS students.

RESULTS

Qualitative Discussion on Best Practices of ALS Volunteered Teachers in Developing the Functional Literacy of Students

ALS volunteer teachers play a significant role in fostering functional literacy among students who have not had the opportunity to complete formal schooling. These dedicated educators employ several best practices to ensure effective learning and skill development. This discussion will explore three key practices utilized by ALS volunteer teachers in developing the functional literacy of their students.

Firstly, ALS volunteer teachers prioritize individualized instruction. They understand that each student has unique learning needs and tailor their teaching methods accordingly. By assessing the abilities and learning styles of their students, volunteer teachers create personalized learning plans. This approach enhances student engagement and promotes better comprehension and retention of literacy skills. Individualized instruction allows volunteer teachers to address the specific challenges faced by students, ensuring their progress towards functional literacy.

Secondly, they utilize relevant and contextualized curriculum. They recognize that functional literacy is best acquired when learning materials are connected to real-life situations. Volunteer teachers incorporate practical examples and scenarios that resonate with the students' daily lives. By presenting literacy skills in a meaningful context, students can understand the practical applications of what they are learning. This approach not only enhances comprehension but also motivates students by demonstrating the value and relevance of functional literacy in their everyday experiences.

Lastly, they employ active learning strategies. They understand that students learn best when they are actively engaged in the learning process. Volunteer teachers encourage participation through group discussions, interactive exercises, and hands-on activities. These strategies promote critical thinking, problem-solving, and effective communication skills. By actively involving students in their learning journey, ALS volunteer teachers empower them to take ownership of their education and develop a deeper understanding of functional literacy.

In conclusion, ALS volunteer teachers employ several best practices to develop functional literacy among their students. By providing individualized instruction, relevant and contextualized curriculum, and incorporating active learning strategies, these educators create an environment conducive to effective learning. Through their dedication and commitment, ALS volunteer teachers empower students to acquire essential literacy skills that will benefit them in various aspects of life. The effect of these best practices extends beyond the classroom, helping individuals overcome educational barriers and become active participants in their communities (Tan, 2018).

Scientific Literacy and Critical thinking Skills

Education is the process of imparting or acquiring general knowledge, developing the powers of reasoning and judgement and generally of preparing oneself or others intellectually for mature life.

As ALS volunteer teachers direct, and indirect instruction methods are effective. Direct instruction is the strategy that influences learners directly in learning. While using the indirect approach gives you a chance or the learner a chance to prove their points and gradually overcome fear of given their own explanation and share their personal experiences about the lesson (Prajapati., Sharma & Sharma, 2017).

Another strategy to help ALS students is to keep verbal instruction short and simple. Cheer them if they understand the directions and guide them through multiple examples and allow them to practice more for better outcomes (Nasheeda, et al., 2019).

Mathematical and Problem-Solving Skills

Providing teachers for specific practices/subject provided a practice said to be best for ALS learners. Teachers for teaching Mathematical and problem-solving skills can think

the activities suited for their level of understanding as well as know the enabling skills needed to teach first to come up with the answers for some problems during examination.

The initiatives of ALS to select teachers for specific areas shows caring and valuing the sense of interest for ALS learners to continue their dreams for their education. For instances for the best practices in dealing this subject in Math, the teacher always relates the problems in their life such as budgeting their money, how much money they pay if they buy goods, paying electricity, water etc. consumption. In this way, ALS learners have their best to interact based on their experiences with regards to math subject and how their problem can solve using the skills they gained as they learn the math subject.

Life and Career Skills

ALS learners are known to be active agents of their own learning. Since ALS program uses a non-formal curriculum that is contextualized and is substantially aligned with the K-12 curriculum, Volunteer-teachers should consider the different indicator of functional literacy such as communication skills, critical thinking, problem solving skills and life and career skills.

ALS learners are encouraged to embrace the principle of lifelong learning when they can see the purpose of the things they learn in the program. When it comes to best practices, ALS volunteer- teachers teach best when they focus on real skills like reading and writing, which given the context of globalized world means using basic cognitive skills to contribute to societal development and social change.

Another best practice of ALS volunteered teachers is ensuring that the learners will graduate with practical skills (mostly on productivity and accountability) so they can improve their chances of employability and widen their livelihood options. Example of this practices is training the learners in building impressive CVs (curriculum vitae) and responding well to interview questions.

Life and career skills like time-Management multi-tasking and even punctuality are good skills to learn in the class. But teachers who want to equip their learners with life and career skills should also teach tolerance and resilience so that their learners will go out to the world ready to tackle whatever life throws their way (D'Arcy, 2014).

Understanding the Self and Society

Education is vital to every human; it serves as the vehicle to become successful in life. That is why the Department of education is making its effort to deliver quality education for the youth in both personal and informal education.

In relation to this, the ALS was provided/introduced to each school to cater out school youth for those who wanted to finish studies at while doing or in their convenient time.

Based on my experience as an ALS completer, the school has various volunteer teachers that will teach us to the best they can. They are not just teaching the subject,

but they also provide series of activities and practices for us to develop our critical thinking skills and creativity. Those are the strategies and approaches that they are using to boost our potential and morale to continue our studies even if we are in not in formal school (Yadav & Pingle, 2017).

Overall, the school gave us a lot of opportunities to enhance our literacy skills by providing real-life activities that would keep us in everyday life. I'm happy that these are teachers who are willing to extend their time to help us the out of school youth individuals like me (Cassidy, 2018).

Digital Citizenship

Alternative Learning System (ALS) volunteered teachers play a crucial role in developing the functional literacy of students. Here are some best practices they can follow:

Individualized Instruction: Recognize that students have different learning needs and abilities. Provide individualized instruction to cater to their specific needs and help them progress at their own pace.

Assess Prior Knowledge: Begin by assessing the students' prior knowledge and skills. This will help you identify their strengths and weaknesses, allowing you to tailor your teaching strategies accordingly.

Use Multisensory Techniques: Incorporate multisensory techniques in your teaching to engage students and enhance their learning experience. Utilize visual aids, hands-on activities, audio materials, and interactive technology to make learning more meaningful and enjoyable.

Active Learning Strategies: Encourage active learning by involving students in the learning process. Use strategies such as group discussions, cooperative learning, role-playing, and problem-solving activities to promote critical thinking, collaboration, and participation.

Real-Life Applications: Emphasize the practical applications of literacy skills in real-life situations. Connect learning to students' everyday experiences and provide examples that demonstrate how literacy skills are relevant and useful (Sobel, 2004).

Contextualized Instruction: Provide instruction that is relevant and meaningful to the students' lives and communities. Incorporate local examples, cultural references, and community-based projects to make learning more relatable and applicable to their surroundings.

Scaffolded Instruction: Break down complex concepts into manageable steps and gradually increase the level of difficulty. Scaffold instruction by providing support, guidance, and additional resources as needed, ensuring that students can grasp and build upon foundational skills.

Regular Assessment and Feedback: Continuously assess students' progress to identify areas that need improvement. Provide timely and constructive feedback to guide their learning. Celebrate their achievements and offer guidance on how they can further enhance their literacy skills.

Collaboration with Parents and Community: Involve parents, guardians, and the broader community in supporting students' literacy development. Organize parent-teacher meetings, community engagement activities, and workshops to foster collaboration and reinforce the importance of literacy in the students' lives.

Professional Development: Engage in continuous professional development to stay updated with the latest teaching strategies and techniques. Attend workshops, conferences, and training sessions related to literacy instruction, adult learning, and teaching methodologies (Vihar, n.d.).

Remember that these best practices should be adapted and tailored to the specific needs of the students you are working with in the ALS program. Flexibility, empathy, and a student-centered approach are key in developing functional literacy skills effectively.

DISCUSSION

The Effect of ALS Volunteered Teachers in the Functional Literacy of ALS Students

Table 1

Computed Mean on Best Practices of ALS Volunteered Teachers in Developing the Functional Literacy of Students in terms of Communication Skills (English and Filipino)

Communication Skills	WM	Verbal Interpretation
1. Volunteered teachers helped me develop my skills in reading, writing, speaking, viewing, and listening both in English and Filipino language.	3.64	Strongly Agree
2. Volunteered teachers guided me in understanding different types of reading texts in developing my reading comprehension skills both in English and Filipino language.	2.80	Agree
3. Volunteered teachers helped me expressed my opinions and feelings through reading and writing activities both in English and Filipino language.	3.68	Strongly Agree
4. Volunteered teachers developed my vocabulary and communication skills.	3.84	Strongly Agree

5. Volunteered teachers helped me develop my language skills specifically in grammar and structure of sentence. and their applications	3.92	Strongly Agree
Overall mean	3.58	Strongly Agree

The findings are summarized as follows: The contribution of volunteered teachers to the enhancement of students' reading, writing, speaking, viewing, and listening skills in both English and Filipino (skill development) is notable, with a WM of 3.64, categorized as "Strongly Agree". The support provided in comprehending various reading materials to improve reading comprehension skills (reading comprehension) received a WM of 2.80, classified as "Agree". The assistance offered in articulating thoughts and emotions through reading and writing activities (expression of thoughts and emotions) achieved a WM of 3.68, categorized as "Strongly Agree". The advancement of vocabulary and communication skills (vocabulary and communication proficiency) was reflected in a high WM of 3.84, interpreted as "Strongly Agree". The aid in enhancing language skills, particularly in grammar and sentence structure (language proficiency) garnered the highest WM of 3.92, classified as "Strongly Agree" The overall mean score stands at 3.58, which is categorized as "Strongly Agree."

It can be inferred from Table 1 that language proficiency obtained the highest mean while reading comprehension has the lowest. This suggests that, on average, students strongly affirm the effectiveness of ALS volunteered teachers in fostering their communication skills.

Table 2

Computed Mean on Best Practices of ALS Volunteered Teachers in Developing the Functional Literacy of Students in terms of Scientific and Critical Thinking Skills

Scientific and Critical Thinking Skills	WM	Verbal Interpretation
1. Volunteered teachers helped me develop my scientific and creative thinking skills.	3.84	Strongly Agree
2. Volunteered teachers helped me demonstrate innovativeness and creativity by coming up with different projects	3.82	Strongly Agree
3. Volunteered teachers helped me apply scientific values and demonstrate positive attitudes in dealing with the advances of science and technology in various life situations	3.76	Strongly Agree
4. Volunteered teachers helped me understand science investigatory projects.	3.76	Strongly Agree
5. Volunteered teachers helped me understand various biological concepts and their applications	3.84	Strongly Agree

Overall mean	3.80	Strongly Agree
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The findings are summarized as follows: The contribution of volunteered teachers to the development of students' scientific and creative thinking skills (enhancement of scientific and creative thinking skills) is notable, with a WM of 3.84, which is interpreted as “Strongly Agree”. The support provided in fostering innovativeness and creativity through various projects (fostering innovativeness and creativity) received a WM of 3.82, also interpreted as “Strongly Agree”. The assistance in applying scientific principles and fostering positive attitudes towards advancements in science and technology in various contexts (application of scientific principles) scored a WM of 3.76, interpreted as “Strongly Agree”. The help provided in understanding science investigatory projects (comprehension of science investigatory projects) also achieved a WM of 3.76, interpreted as “Strongly Agree”. The support in comprehending various biological concepts and their applications (grasp of biological concepts) yielded a high WM of 3.84, interpreted as “Strongly Agree”.

It can be inferred from Table 2 that enhancement of scientific and creative thinking skills and grasp of biological concepts obtained the highest mean while application of scientific principles and comprehension of science investigatory projects have the lowest. The overall mean score is 3.80, which is categorized as “Strongly Agree”. This suggests that, on average, students strongly affirm the effectiveness of ALS volunteered teachers in enhancing their scientific and critical thinking skills.

Table 3

Computed Mean on Best Practices of ALS Volunteered Teachers in Developing the Functional Literacy of Students in terms of Mathematical and Problem-Solving Skills

Mathematical and Problem-Solving Skills	WM	Verbal Interpretation
1. Volunteered teachers helped me develop my mathematical and problem-Solving Skills through different practice exercises.	3.70	Strongly Agree
2. Volunteered teachers helped me realized the importance and value of mathematics as a means of communicating and solving problems in daily life.	3.62	Strongly Agree
3. Volunteered teachers helped me demonstrate comprehension of whole numbers and their uses in everyday life.	3.62	Strongly Agree
4. Volunteered teachers helped me exhibit honesty and accuracy in collecting and reporting mathematical data.	3.56	Strongly Agree

5. Volunteered teachers helped me integrate mathematics with disciplines such as economics, agricultural studies, communication arts, science and technology, geography, cooking, architecture and music.	3.44	Strongly Agree
Overall mean	3.60	Strongly Agree

The findings are summarized as follows: Volunteered teachers played a crucial role in fostering students' mathematical and problem-solving skills through a variety of practice exercises (enhancement of mathematical and problem-solving abilities), achieving a WM of 3.70, which is interpreted as “Strongly Agree”. The guidance provided in recognizing the significance and utility of mathematics as a tool for communication and problem-solving in everyday situations (significance of mathematics) received a WM of 3.62, also interpreted as “Strongly Agree”. The support in illustrating the understanding of whole numbers and their practical applications (understanding of whole numbers) scored a WM of 3.62, interpreted as “Strongly Agree”. Assistance in demonstrating integrity and precision in the collection and reporting of mathematical data (integrity and precision in data) resulted in a WM of 3.56, interpreted as “Strongly Agree”. The support for integrating mathematics with other fields such as economics, agricultural studies, communication arts, science and technology, geography, culinary arts, architecture, and music (interdisciplinary integration) received a WM of 3.44, interpreted as “Strongly Agree”. The overall mean score is 3.60, which is categorized as “Strongly Agree”.

It can be explained from the result that majority of the respondents claimed that there is enhancement of mathematical and problem-solving abilities which got the highest mean of while interdisciplinary integration got the lowest mean. This suggests that, on average, students strongly affirm the effectiveness of ALS volunteered teachers in enhancing their mathematical and problem-solving skills.

Table 4

Computed Mean on Best Practices of ALS Volunteered Teachers in Developing the Functional Literacy of Students in terms of Understanding the Self and Society

Understanding the Self and Society	WM	Verbal Interpretation
1. Volunteered teachers helped me realize the importance of showing appreciation for achieving one’s goal	3.70	Strongly Agree
2. Volunteered teachers helped me to show ways of managing/controlling negative feeling.	3.62	Strongly Agree
3. Volunteered teachers helped me strengthen one’s personal conviction by taking a stand on social issues	3.62	Strongly Agree

4. Volunteered teachers helped me develop one's potential by being open to the suggestions of others, showing willingness to effect change.	3.56	Strongly Agree
5. Volunteered teachers helped me to show respect for others through tolerance, acceptance of others, and appreciation of differences in ideas, feelings, and beliefs.	3.44	Agree
Overall mean	3.60	Strongly Agree

In the significance of expressing gratitude (statement 1), the average score stands at 3.70, signifying a strong consensus. Acknowledging and valuing accomplishments is vital for individual development and motivation. Managing negative emotions (statement 2), with an average score of 3.62, shows there is a strong agreement that volunteered educators assisted them in managing and regulating negative emotions. Emotional health is essential for self-awareness. In advocating for social issues (statement 3), the average score is 3.62, indicating strong agreement. Volunteered educators motivated them to reinforce their personal beliefs by engaging with social issues, which promotes critical thinking and empathy. Cultivating potential and receptiveness (statement 4) is rated with strong agreement at 3.56. Being receptive to feedback and welcoming change are important attributes for personal growth and societal influence. Demonstrating respect for others (statement 5) has an average score of 3.44 suggesting that volunteered educators highlighted the importance of respect through tolerance, acceptance, and appreciation of diverse perspectives, emotions, and beliefs. These attributes enhance harmonious interactions within the community.

It can be delineated for the result that “Volunteered teachers helped me realize the importance of showing appreciation for achieving one’s goal” got the highest mean, while “Volunteered teachers helped me to show respect for others through tolerance, acceptance of others, and appreciation of differences in ideas, feelings, and beliefs” got the lowest. The overall average of 3.60 emphasizes the beneficial influence of volunteered educators on their functional literacy concerning self-awareness and societal understanding. (Shek, et. al. 2020).

Table 5

Computed Mean on Best Practices of ALS Volunteered Teachers in Developing the Functional Literacy of Students in terms of Life and Career Skills

Life and Career Skills	WM	Verbal Interpretation
1. Volunteered teachers helped me develop my personal strengths/attributes/assets/limitation/interests as a potential employee	3.64	Strongly Agree

2. Volunteered teachers made me appreciate the importance of planning for life and career development	3.64	Strongly Agree
3. Volunteered teachers helped me demonstrate an awareness of occupations in the local and global community and understand the interdependence of these occupations	3.44	Strongly Agree
4. Volunteered teachers helped me to identify competency requirements for different career options	3.56	Strongly Agree
5. Volunteered teachers helped me identify possible career options aligned with one's interest/strengths/assets	3.58	Strongly Agree
Overall mean	3.57	Strongly Agree

Developing personal strengths and attributes (statement 1) has an average score for that stands at 3.64, reflecting a strong consensus. Volunteered educators have been instrumental in assisting you in recognizing and cultivating your personal strengths, attributes, and limitations—key characteristics for prospective employees. Appreciating the importance of planning (statement 2), with an average score of 3.64, shows there is a strong agreement that volunteered educators highlighted the importance of planning for both life and career development. Effective planning facilitates a deliberate and strategic method for achieving objectives. Awareness of occupations (statement 3) has an average score of 3.44 indicating strong agreement. Volunteered educators have contributed to their awareness of various occupations, both locally and internationally, promoting an understanding of their interconnections. Identifying competency requirements (statement 4) have expression of strong agreement with a rating of 3.56. Recognizing the competency requirements for various career paths is crucial for making informed choices. Aligning career options with interests and strengths (statement 5) has an average score of 3.58 suggesting that volunteered educators effectively assisted them in identifying career options that correspond with your interests, strengths, and assets. This tailored approach significantly enhances your career opportunities.

It can be reflected from Table 5 that “Volunteered teachers helped me develop my personal strengths/attributes/assets/limitation/interests as a potential employee” and “Volunteered teachers made me appreciate the importance of planning for life and career development” got the highest mean, while “Volunteered teachers helped me demonstrate an awareness of occupations in the local and global community and understand the interdependence of these occupations” got the lowest. The overall mean of 3.57 highlights the beneficial influence of volunteered educators on your functional literacy concerning life and career skills.

Table 6

Computed Mean on Best Practices of ALS Volunteered Teachers in Developing the Functional Literacy of Students in terms of Digital Citizenship

Digital Citizenship	WM	Verbal Interpretation
1. Volunteered teachers helped me identify the different potential problems of a desktop computer.	3.60	Strongly Agree
2. Volunteered teachers helped me demonstrate the procedure of troubleshooting basic problems of a desktop computer	3.80	Strongly Agree
3. Volunteered teachers helped me demonstrate how to save a document as another file type like: rich text format, word template, PDF and web page	3.78	Strongly Agree
4. Volunteered teachers helped me save documents under another name to a location on a Drive	3.82	Strongly Agree
5. Volunteered teachers helped me being knowledgeable in using MS Word, PowerPoint Presentations.	3.66	Strongly Agree
Overall mean	3.73	Strongly Agree

It is commendable to observe the beneficial influence of volunteered educators on your digital literacy and comprehension of digital citizenship. Identifying potential problems of a desktop computer (statement 1) has an average rating that stands at 3.60, signifying a strong level of agreement. Recognizing common computer issues is crucial for effective troubleshooting and ensuring operational efficiency. Troubleshooting basic problems (statement 2), with an average rating of 3.80, shows there is a strong consensus that volunteered educators effectively demonstrated the methods for addressing basic desktop computer issues. This hands-on knowledge proves to be invaluable in daily applications. Saving documents in different file formats (statement 3) has an average rating of 3.78 that indicates strong agreement. The ability to save documents in various formats (such as rich text, Word template, PDF, and web page) significantly enhances adaptability and interoperability. Renaming and saving documents (statement 4) have expression of strong agreement with a rating of 3.82. Volunteered educators facilitated their understanding of how to save documents under different names and organize them effectively on a Drive. MS Word and PowerPoint skills (statement 5) has an average rating of 3.66 suggesting that volunteered educators have played a significant role in enhancing their proficiency in using MS Word and creating PowerPoint presentations. These competencies are essential in both academic and professional environments.

It can be shown from the results that “Volunteered teachers helped me save documents under another name to a location on a Drive” got the highest mean, while “Volunteered teachers helped me Identify the different potential problems of a desktop computer” got the lowest. The overall mean of 3.73 highlights the effectiveness of volunteered educators in improving your digital literacy and practical skills associated with digital citizenship.

Conclusions

In line with the dissemination of the research conducted, this was disseminated to all Junior high school teachers, department heads, group heads, ALS advocate in strengthening the functional literacy of ALS students. Also, during the in-service training conducted for teachers and to produce multiple action research from the ALS initiatives and best practices.

The basis for proposed action plan were the results of the survey:

1. The data presented in Table 1 indicates that language proficiency achieved the highest mean score, whereas reading comprehension recorded the lowest. This implies that, on average, students strongly recognize the effectiveness of ALS volunteered teachers in enhancing their communication skills.
2. According to the findings in Table 2, the development of scientific and creative thinking skills, along with the understanding of biological concepts, received the highest mean score, while the application of scientific principles and comprehension of science investigatory projects received the lowest. The overall mean score suggests that, on average, students strongly acknowledge the effectiveness of ALS volunteered teachers in improving their scientific and critical thinking abilities.
3. The results indicate that a significant majority of respondents reported an improvement in their mathematical and problem-solving skills, which received the highest mean score, while interdisciplinary integration received the lowest mean score. This suggests that, on average, students strongly affirm the effectiveness of ALS volunteered teachers in enhancing their mathematical and problem-solving capabilities.
4. The results reveal that expressing gratitude received the highest mean score, while the demonstration respect for others received the lowest. The overall average score highlights the positive impact of volunteered educators on students' functional literacy regarding self-awareness and social understanding.
5. It can be reflected from the results that developing personal strengths and attributes, and appreciate the importance of planning got the highest mean, while awareness of occupations got the lowest. The overall mean highlights the beneficial influence of volunteered educators on your functional literacy concerning life and career skills.

6. It can be shown from the results that renaming and saving documents got the highest mean, while identifying potential problems of a desktop computer got the lowest. The overall mean highlights the effectiveness of volunteered educators in improving your digital literacy and practical skills associated with digital citizenship.

Recommendations

As such as based on the results, the proposed action plan for the development of ALS teachers are as follows:

1. Recruiting ALS volunteer teachers
 2. Training of ALS volunteer teachers
 3. Development of ALS Modules that will be used with an integration of thematic teaching, interactive and cooperative learning.
 4. Distribution of ALS volunteers to their respective assignments.
 5. Conduct Quarterly meetings with the Schools ALS Leaders of the district/school.
 6. Intense review and teaching the learners to become prepared for the A & E Test and final assessment; and
 7. Develop learning materials that include print materials and internet resources and other materials to support learning instruction.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

This is a paragraph-form declaration by the author or authors that covers the following topics: compliance with obtaining informed consent; respondents' freedom to withdraw from the study at any time; respondents' anonymity was maintained; respondents' well-being was protected; no conflict of interest existed in the study's conduct; strict avoidance of plagiarism; no bias existed in the interpretation of the results; and that the results were used only for research.

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REFERENCES

- Bukidnon State University. (2018). *Extension Project: Capacitating Alternative Learning System Information Education Teaching in Teaching Life Skills*.
- Cassidy, K. (2018). Preparation for adulthood: A teacher inquiry study for facilitating life skills in secondary education in the United States. *Journal of Educational Issues*, 4(1), 33-46.
- Commission on Higher Education (2017). Commission Memorandum Order No. 83, s. 2017: Policies, Standards, and Guidelines for the Post Baccalaureate Diploma in Alternative Learning System.
- D'Arcy, K. (2014). *Literature review: What do we know about life skills and leadership training for vulnerable children and young people?* European Union.
- Department of Education (2019). *Alternative learning system – education and skills training: Handbook for implementers*.
- Miriam College SDTEC (n.d.). *Alternative learning system*.
<https://www.mc.edu.ph/sdtec/als>
- Moyer, C. D. (2016). *A thematic instruction approach to teaching technology and engineering*. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1118760>
- Nasheeda, A., Abdullah, H. B., Krauss, S. E., & Ahmed, N. B. (2019). A narrative systematic review of life skills education: Effectiveness, research gaps and priorities. *International Journal of Adolescence and Youth*, 24(3), 362-379. DOI: 10.1080/02673843.2018.1479278.
- Ocampo, D. M. (2021). Functional literacy of alternative learning system (ALS) learners: Basis for sustainable extension activity development. *Online Submission*, 5(2), 359–368.
- Philippine News Agency (2020). *House OKs bill institutionalizing alternative learning system*. <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1111916>.
- Prajapati, R., Sharma, B., & Sharma, D. (2017). Significance of life skills education. *Contemporary Issues in Education Research*, 10(1), 1-6.
- Shek, D. T. L., Lin, L., Ma, C. M. S., Yu, L., Leung, J. T. Y., Wu, F. K. Y., Leung, H., & Dou, D. (2020). Perceptions of adolescents, teachers and parents of life skills education and life skills in high school. *Applied Research in Quality of Life*. Springer. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11482-020-09848-9>
- Sobel, D. (2004). Place-based education: Connection classroom and community. *Nature and Listening*. Antioch University New England.

- Tan, S. (2018). *Life skills education: Teachers' perceptions in primary school classrooms in Finland and Singapore. A thesis.* University of Jyväskylä. Department of Education. <https://bit.ly/3hWiOr3>.
- UNESCO (2006). *Literacy: The core of education for all.* UNESDOC Digital Library.
- Vihar, P. (n.d.). *Life skills education.* Central Board of Secondary Education.
- Yadav, S. B., & Pingle, S. S. (2017). Development of life skills programme and study: Its effect on life skills ability of students. *Indian Streams Research Journal*, 7(2), 1-13.
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